
Siradel Solution for Automatic Cell Planning of Distributed MIMO Networks

A coverage–cost study of Automatic Cell Selection (ACS) for industrial 6G deployments

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Topic Distributed-MIMO (D-MIMO) network planning

Scenario Factory-floor industrial site (210 m x 97 m), 136 candidate AP positions

Executive Summary

Siradel provides end-to-end decision-support solutions for wireless network planning e.g. for local 5G, Fixed Wireless Access (FWA), Internet of Things (IoT) or 5G railway deployments. This White Paper examines automatic network design for a key 6G candidate technology, namely cell-free **Distributed MIMO** (D-MIMO). The present study is part of the French collaborative research project POSEIDON, which aims to improve and demonstrate the performance of this emerging technology in factory and urban environments.

Unlike traditional deployment, the goal here is to maximize the number of APs that can cooperate constructively at each reception point, so as to optimize service availability and data rates. The present study does not predict all D-MIMO network performance metrics in detail, but builds on previous work carried out within the POSEIDON project to establish a link between simple metrics (RSRP and AP overlap) and connection efficiency.

An **automatic cell selection (ACS)** tool is applied to a factory scenario with 136 candidate access-point (AP) positions operating at 3.7 GHz. Several design solutions are achieved and compared by sweeping three signal-quality thresholds, three AP-cooperation (overlap) levels, and six different coverage targets.

The automatic AP selection is completed with an **interactive dashboard** that compares and analyses candidate deployments against the criteria chosen by the user. By sweeping three

parameters — the cooperation level between APs, the minimum RSRP, and the target coverage percentage — the method turns a large space of design options into a compact set of clear, quantified trade-offs. This lets network designers set right-sized objectives matched to their actual needs, and decide where to place APs, how many to deploy, and at what cooperation level — all well before any hardware is installed on site.

Across the design space, three effects dominate: the RSRP threshold is the largest cost driver; higher cooperation order requires proportionally more APs; coverage shows strong diminishing returns near full coverage.

1 Introduction

Automatic Cell Selection (ACS) addresses a single core question: how many access points (APs) should be deployed, and at which of the available candidate positions, so that a target service area is covered at a prescribed signal quality while the infrastructure cost is kept to a minimum. In a **6G cell-free Distributed-MIMO (D-MIMO)** deployment, this question is reframed. Rather than partitioning the area into cells, each served by a single base station, a large set of distributed APs jointly serve every user; planning therefore becomes the joint selection of an AP subset and of the degree of cooperation between APs.

The analysis presented here is based on an **ACS** study carried out for a 6G deployment in an industrial (factory-floor) environment with 136 candidate AP positions operating at 3.7 GHz (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Factory area and candidate AP locations.

An ACS algorithm selects a subset of APs from **136 candidate locations** to satisfy a given coverage objective. For the link budget, each AP transmits a total Tx power of 23 dBm over 40 MHz of bandwidth, and a location is considered covered when its received RSRP exceeds a configurable threshold for at least the target number of overlapping APs.

2 Design Parameter Space

Each planning scenario is defined by three families of parameters:

- **Minimum RSRP (signal-quality threshold).** Three thresholds are considered — -80 dBm (excellent), -100 dBm (good) and -120 dBm (fair). A stricter threshold requires a denser deployment to keep every covered location above the limit.
- **Target overlap — the AP cooperation order.** The overlap level is the number of APs that jointly serve each covered location, and it is the design proxy criterion most directly tied to D-MIMO. Overlap 1 is a single-AP, cellular-like baseline, whereas Overlap 2 and Overlap 3 are the D-MIMO regimes of interest. This choice is motivated by prior work showing that cooperation among up to three APs significantly improves system performance, while cooperation beyond three APs brings only limited additional gains [1, 2]. For instance, in [1] and in the same factory environment, authors showed that under cooperation, the benefit of distributing antennas to exploit diversity is clear, but a threshold effect appears: beyond a certain number of cooperating APs, 3 in this scenario, no further diversity gain is achieved. As the cooperating APs are selected on received power, increasing cooperation beyond 3 APs brings limited benefit — the diversity is largely reached and the focus shifts to users close to the APs, whose channels are predominantly LoS with good SNR.
- **Coverage target.** The fraction of the service area that must reach the RSRP threshold and the target overlap, swept from 60% to 99% according to the application type and the required connectivity level.

3 Design Results

Crossing the three dimensions cited in the previous section ($3 \times 3 \times 6$) produces the **54 design points** reported in Table 1. For each point, the ACS algorithm returns two outputs: the number of selected APs (and their locations) — reflecting the deployment cost, out of 136 candidates — and the reached coverage (i.e. the coverage actually achieved).

Table 1. ACS automatic cell-planning results: selected APs and reached coverage for all 54 configurations.

AP selection results

Min RSRP = -120 dBm				Min RSRP = -100 dBm				Min RSRP = -80 dBm			
Overlap	Target (%)	Sel. APs (of 136)	Reached cov. (%)	Overlap	Target (%)	Sel. APs (of 136)	Reached cov. (%)	Overlap	Target (%)	Sel. APs (of 136)	Reached cov. (%)
1	60	2	72.28	1	60	4	67.97	1	60	14	61.40
1	70	2	72.28	1	70	5	74.68	1	70	19	71.09
1	80	3	85.25	1	80	7	84.42	1	80	26	80.98
1	90	4	92.37	1	90	10	91.96	1	90	39	90.06
1	95	6	96.90	1	95	14	95.40	1	95	63	95.03
1	99	9	99.12	1	99	50	98.45	1	99	101	96.11
2	60	4	64.13	2	60	10	60.85	2	60	38	60.70
2	70	6	79.38	2	70	12	70.29	2	70	49	70.53
2	80	7	85.03	2	80	16	81.49	2	80	62	80.28
2	90	9	90.96	2	90	20	90.12	2	90	101	90.08
2	95	12	95.05	2	95	28	95.25	2	95	129	90.95
2	99	20	99.08	2	99	70	97.53	2	99	129	90.95
3	60	7	61.49	3	60	16	61.47	3	60	67	61.19
3	70	9	73.56	3	70	20	71.21	3	70	81	70.01
3	80	11	83.99	3	80	26	81.89	3	80	115	80.09
3	90	14	90.23	3	90	32	90.07	3	90	136	81.31
3	95	19	95.52	3	95	42	95.05	3	95	136	81.31
3	99	33	99.04	3	99	86	97.17	3	99	136	81.31

Figure 2. Resulting overlap map (left) and coverage map (right) for following objective: Min RSRP -100 dBm, Overlap 3, 80% target.

Figure 2 shows two representative spatial results:

- **Left:** the per-location count of serving APs across the factory floor, with the selected AP positions overlaid as markers (warm colors indicate locations served by more APs, i.e. higher overlap).

- **Right:** the covered (green) and uncovered (blue) areas for the selected target, defined by a minimum overlap and a required RSRP per AP. This identifies the coverage holes where the network cannot deliver the required service, which helps first to understand why the propagation conditions are not favorable, and then either to route AGVs around these areas or to flag them for densification.

Once Siradel's ACS engine provides the best candidate deployment for each defined objective, we turn these raw selection results into actionable insights through an interactive dashboard. Together, the dashboard and the ACS engine form a complete decision-support chain — from candidate-site selection and coverage computation through visual comparison to the final deployment decision — giving network planners a sound, evidence-based footing for their choices. The dashboard, published online [3], makes exploring the results straightforward: the user selects a target configuration (minimum RSRP, overlap level, and coverage target) and instantly obtains the full corresponding output — the number of selected APs, the reached coverage, the overlap / RSRP / coverage maps, and a 3D view of the site with the selected APs overlaid.

4 The Coverage–Cost Trade-off

The central planning result is the relationship between reached coverage and the number of deployed APs, shown in Figure 3 for all 54 configurations (color = cooperation level, line style = RSRP threshold).

Figure 3. Reached coverage versus number of selected APs.

Three behaviors dominate the design space.

4.1 Diminishing returns

Every curve climbs steeply and then flattens: the final few percent of coverage is by far the most expensive. With Min RSRP -100 dBm and Overlap 1, the first 90% coverage is reached with only 10 APs, but raising the target from 95% to 99% drives the selection from 14 to 50 APs — roughly an order of magnitude more APs for the last few percent. Practical designs should therefore sit before the knee of the curve.

4.2 Cost of signal quality (Min RSRP)

Tightening the RSRP threshold is the most expensive lever. At Overlap 2 and a 90% target, meeting -120 dBm requires 9 APs, -100 dBm requires 20, and -80 dBm requires 101 APs — an order-of-magnitude increase driven purely by the quality requirement (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Number of selected APs versus cooperation (overlap) level at a 90% coverage target, for each RSRP threshold.

4.3 Cost of cooperation (overlap)

For a fixed threshold and target, higher overlap costs more APs because more APs must simultaneously reach each location. At -100 dBm and a 90% target the selection grows from 10 APs (Overlap 1) to 20 (Overlap 2) to 32 (Overlap 3) (Figure 5); broadly, Overlap 3 requires about 1.5–3× the APs of Overlap 2. This is the direct infrastructure cost of the AP cooperation that underpins D-MIMO.

In sum, there is a clear trade-off between **coverage performance** and **deployment cost**: tightening the quality target and raising the overlap level improves coverage uniformity, but only through a denser and more expensive network — so the **operating point** must be chosen to balance the two rather than to maximize coverage in isolation.

Note that at -80 dBm the required AP count plateaus for target overlaps of 2 and 3 (129 and 136 APs, respectively), yet the achieved coverage stops rising: both configurations hit a ceiling well below target, reaching only about 91% and 81% against a 99% objective. This raises the question

of whether the -80 dBm requirement could be relaxed in parts of the factory when an overlap of 2 or 3 is targeted.

Figure 5. Growth of the number of selected APs with the coverage target, at Min RSRP -100 dBm.

5 Planning Implications for D-MIMO

Taken together, the results define a practical operating envelope for D-MIMO cell planning in this industrial setting. D-MIMO operation (overlap 2–3) is achievable across most of the target range at the -120 dBm and -100 dBm thresholds with a moderate AP budget, while delivering the multi-AP cooperation that improves link reliability and spectral efficiency for multi-user industrial traffic. This envelope is consistent with the throughput and energy-efficiency behavior reported for the same factory scenario in the POSEIDON link- and system-level studies: the single-user capacity saturates beyond a few cooperating APs [1, Fig. 8], the multi-user spectral-efficiency gain over a co-located deployment flattens as AP density grows [2, Fig. 3], and the network energy efficiency is maximized at a low-to-moderate AP count — typically 2 to 4 APs — with simple AP selection more energy-efficient than coherent joint transmission [2, Table 2,3]. In short, a moderate density providing overlap 2–3 already captures most of the achievable capacity at the best energy trade-off, whereas over-densification yields diminishing throughput returns at rising power and fronthaul cost. Three guidelines follow:

- (i) keep the design before the knee of the coverage–cost curve, typically at coverage targets up to about 90–95%, to avoid the steep cost tail — which is also where the spectral- and energy-efficiency gains of densification begin to saturate in the POSEIDON evaluations;
- (ii) treat the RSRP threshold as the dominant cost driver and relax it to $-100/-120$ dBm wherever the application permits, since the throughput and reliability benefits of additional APs are limited beyond a moderate density;
- (iii) treat the -80 dBm threshold as a highly stringent objective, to be applied only in areas or along trajectories with particularly high capacity demand, where the extra AP count and energy

consumption are justified by the throughput requirement. Note that, in case of an operational design exercise, it is possible to define customized objectives for multiple sub-areas.

References

- [1] JAZIRI, Aymen, DEMMER, David, CORRE, Yoann, et al. Comparative analysis of ray tracing and Rayleigh fading models for distributed MIMO systems in industrial environments. In: 2025 19th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP). IEEE, 2025. p. 1-5.
- [2] DEMMER, David, JAZIRI, Aymen, BELDI, Chaima, et al. Performance Analysis of Multi-User Distributed MIMO Networks for Industrial Applications using Ray-Tracing Modeling. In: 2025 IEEE 36th International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC). IEEE, 2025. p. 1-6.
- [3] HTML dashboard, associated to this white paper, available at [SIRADEL D-MIMO automated network design | Zenodo](#).